

CommuniCity

Innovative Solutions Responding to the Needs
of Cities & Communities

D2.9 Principles for ethical and inclusive engagement.

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D2.9 Principles of ethical and inclusive engagement

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Lead Partner:	Amsterdam University of Applied Science
Editors:	Nick Verouden, AUAS Sophie Vermaning, AUAS Tamara Witschge, AUAS
Reviewers:	Hugo Kerschot, OASC Silja Peltonen, FVH Ethics Board (Pernille Tranberg, Adele Bucella, Vito Michele Pavese)
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Executive Summary

This Deliverable (D2.9) presents the final principles of ethical and inclusive engagement, developed from research conducted by AUAS during two rounds of the CommuniCity pilots, described in D2.8 and the impact study undertaken in 6.3. These principles aim to guide stakeholders in adapting solutions to the specific needs of local communities, especially marginalized groups, in smart city contexts. Five key principles are identified, each offering actionable guidelines for future co-creation initiatives:

1. **Champion Inclusivity:** Ensure equal and meaningful participation by engaging communities early and removing barriers to participation.
2. **Strengthen Connections:** Build trust through transparent communication, active listening, and acknowledging cultural, language, and geographical differences.
3. **Coordinate with Empathy:** Address challenges proactively by clarifying roles and providing flexibility in timelines and budgets for community participation.
4. **Open Up to Context:** Adapt co-creation efforts to the community's unique needs and foster lasting support networks for long-term resilience.
5. **Frame the Bigger Picture:** Guide co-creation with a clear vision focused on social, ethical, and cultural goals, emphasizing long-term sustainability.

In conclusion, these guidelines help stakeholders adapt solutions to the needs of local, marginalized communities. Focusing on inclusivity, empathy, and context ensures equitable, sustainable outcomes in future smart city co-creation initiatives. By embracing these principles, stakeholders can create lasting, meaningful change. We conclude this deliverable by presenting the Co-Creation Reboot Card Set, developed by AUAS based on the principles of ethical and inclusive engagement, designed to integrate reflexivity into the piloting process. This final deliverable has been reviewed by the Ethics Board through meetings and written feedback, and their input has been incorporated into the final version.

1. Introduction: Scope and approach

In this Deliverable (D2.9) we present the final principles of ethical and inclusive engagement based on research from two rounds of CommuniCity pilots. These principles are aimed at facilitating stakeholders to effectively adapt existing solutions to meet the specific needs of local communities, including hard-to-reach and marginalized communities. This report builds on insights from D2.8 and integrates findings from the impact study conducted in wp/task 6.3 (Impact Analysis of Communities). It synthesizes key findings from both D2.8 and our impact analysis of co-creation sessions during the CommuniCity project.

This report first outlines the steps in our research taken to define the final principles, providing context for their development and refinement. Next, we introduce five key principles of ethical and inclusive engagement, each offering concrete, actionable guidance for future co-creation initiatives with marginalized communities in smart cities contexts. Finally, we present a visual representation of the principles, offering a clear and accessible overview of their interconnections and practical application.

Steps taken towards defining principles

Ethical and inclusive engagement is fundamental to co-creation because it ensures that participatory processes are not only collaborative but also fair, impactful, and sustainable. Without such foundational principles, co-creation risks reinforcing existing power imbalances, excluding marginalized voices, and failing to achieve meaningful impact (Costanza, 2020). Such principles provide a clear yet adaptable foundation, helping participants navigate the complexities of working across diverse communities, disciplines, and interests in inclusive and ethical ways. In this sense they are not just abstract ideals but practical commitments that shape design processes, ensuring that they are participatory, equitable, and accountable. As Pink et al. (2022) highlight, in today's rapidly evolving societies and organizations, design principles help shape responsible and ethical futures. They serve as essential tools for learning, strategic planning, vision-building, and intervention design—influencing industries, policymaking, and activism alike. By integrating ethical and inclusive engagement principles, co-creation can move beyond symbolic participation, fostering genuine collaboration that leads to meaningful, lasting change.

In this research, the first step in defining principles of ethical and inclusive engagement was to develop and refine a set of good practices based on research, practitioner insights, and pilot experiences. In preparation for the first round of CommuniCity pilots (May–September 2023), the Municipality of Amsterdam and the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS) compiled a list of good co-creation

practices. This list was initially developed in December 2022, based on interviews with municipal officers experienced in co-creation, supplemented by AUAS's review of participatory and co-design literature (see D.2.8 for a full research description).

Following the first round of pilots, the list of exemplary practices was revised based on feedback from pilot participants, observations from the municipality, and additional research insights. A final revision in September 2023 laid the foundation for the first draft of the principles of ethical and inclusive engagement presented in deliverable D2.8. Insights from the updated list were translated into practical tips and shared with the second-round pilot teams to support ethical and inclusive co-creation.

The second step was to refine the initial list of good practices into a set of preliminary principles, informed by research conducted during the first round of pilots. Through this analysis, four key themes emerged, each addressing specific challenges in collaborating with marginalized or vulnerable communities. These themes—proximity and diversity; definitional clarity and equity; mediation and community representation; and temporal clarity, expectations, and strategic alignment—were further developed by integrating insights from relevant literature and the initial principles proposed by practice partners. Together, these elements contributed to a framework for ethical and inclusive engagement, which is aimed at ensuring that co-creation efforts remain responsive to the complexities and needs of the communities involved.

The final step aimed to expand and refine these initial principles through ongoing empirical research within WP6 of the CommuniCity project. This phase included supplementary qualitative research conducted by AUAS during the second round of pilots, with a stronger focus on assessing the impact of the co-creation methodology used to adapt existing solutions (see report D6.4 for a full description of the impact analysis). Building on insights from Deliverable D2.8 and the co-creation impact analysis (6.3), we distilled our findings and identified five core principles: *Champion Inclusivity*, *Strengthen Connections*, *Coordinate with Empathy*, *Open Up to Context*, and *Frame the Bigger Picture*.

Together, these principles form the "Final Principles of Ethical and Inclusive Engagement"—a framework designed to help stakeholders design and practice co-creation processes that are adaptive and responsive to the unique needs of each specific community, challenge, and pilot. The remainder of this report outlines these principles, providing actionable recommendations to enhance future co-creation initiatives in smart cities contexts and beyond.

2. Final Principles of Ethical and Inclusive Engagement

This section presents the final set of principles, shaped by our research and experiences with the CommuniCity pilots. Each principle includes a brief description and is accompanied by actionable guidelines to enhance ethical and inclusive engagement in future smart city co-creation initiatives. By addressing key challenges identified during the project, these guidelines provide clear strategies to refine co-creation processes and foster meaningful participation.

2.1. Principle 1. Champion inclusivity

The first principle highlights that inclusivity goes beyond simply inviting community members to participate in co-creation sessions—it requires proactively ensuring equal and meaningful participation of community members throughout the entire process. This involves removing barriers and enhancing accessibility, including physical, digital, and linguistic, while fostering an environment where all community members, regardless of ability or background, can meaningfully contribute, influence decisions, and shape both the process and its outcomes. Additionally, it calls for ongoing recognition and discussion of power dynamics, as inequalities related to gender, race, class, disability, and education—both explicit and implicit—persist in co-creation and can hinder inclusivity. Power dynamics do not simply vanish when participants engage in co-creation.

To achieve this, it is essential to:

- **Engage communities early, directly and continuously**

Engage and involve community members from the start, especially when identifying and formulating design challenges. Give them a leading role in shaping the process and establish clear, open communication channels to ensure their perspectives are genuinely heard, valued and represented at every stage of the process. This approach should continue throughout the entire process to maintain meaningful participation.

- **Ensure that multiple perspectives are represented**

Ensure that the voice of the different stakeholders in the process are represented, including those that may challenge your own ideas, perspectives or assumptions. Co-creation is built on championing diverse perspectives. Take proactive steps in reaching out to include perspectives of stakeholders that are easily overlooked or dismissed, fostering a more inclusive and representative process. Recognize that some community members may need additional support and encouragement to provide input into the process. Regularly

check in with underrepresented groups to ensure their voices are heard and create accessible channels for them to contribute their ideas and feedback.

- **Embrace compromise**

Approach co-creation with flexibility by balancing diverse needs, perspectives, and interests, recognizing that compromise is key to adaptation and finding common ground for more inclusive outcomes. At the same time, identify and uphold non-negotiable values or principles that maintain the integrity of the process. Ensure that compromises do not undermine these core values. Regularly check in with participants to confirm that the decisions made are not eroding the project's fundamental principles and be open to adjusting the process as needed to stay aligned with its core values.

- **Reframe power dynamics**

Reframe power dynamics by shifting from labeling communities as "marginalized" or "vulnerable" to recognizing them as active experts of their own experiences. Foster an environment of mutual respect where communities feel empowered to share their knowledge. Actively surface power dynamics throughout the process to ensure equal participation and decision-making and take concrete steps to address any imbalances that arise.

2.2. Principle 2. Strengthen connections

The second principle holds that co-creation relies on cultivating trust and fostering meaningful relationships between all parties involved—designers, community members, facilitators, and decision-makers. Co-creation actively reshapes how people interact, influencing power structures and introducing fresh challenges in maintaining balanced and inclusive relationships. Addressing these dynamics requires investing time in engaging with community members in their own environments and on their terms, which helps to respect and integrate existing community dynamics. Establishing trust requires transparent and consistent communication, where every participant feels valued and heard. Building trust is a gradual process and takes time, requiring active listening, following through on commitments, and creating safe spaces for authentic participation. Trust-based relationships ensure that community members' voices are genuinely valued, and decisions are made collaboratively, with equal and fair consideration of all perspectives.

To achieve this, it is essential to:

- **Invest in building strong relationships**

Dedicate time to cultivating trust by creating safe spaces for authentic community

participation. Respect existing community dynamics and actively visit and engage with communities in their local environments and on their terms.

- **Build and maintain trust**

Foster trust through transparent, open communication and consistency. Ensure that all parties, including community members, are genuinely valued. Build relationships over time by actively listening, following through on commitments, and creating spaces where everyone feels safe to contribute. Especially when working with geographically distributed teams, be mindful of cultural and language differences and integrate them into your approach. Foster relationships and ensure that distance does not weaken collaboration.

- **Stay open to learning from others**

Adopt a learning mindset by embracing feedback and insights from a diversity of community members and stakeholders. Make sure you listen, reflect and refine during the process. This commitment to ongoing reflection allows for mutual growth and helps refine co-creation practices over time, ensuring relevance and inclusivity.

- **Avoid tokenism**

Genuine relationships go beyond surface-level inclusion. "Do no harm" requires moving beyond performative engagement, where community voices are acknowledged but not meaningfully acted upon, to prevent frustration and disillusionment.

- **Cultivate shared ownership**

Create opportunities for all stakeholders to shape decisions and processes from the outset. Recognize community expertise as equally (or even more) valuable as institutional or professional knowledge.

2.3. Principle 3. Coordinate with empathy

The third principle emphasizes that coordination and organizational challenges in co-creation efforts must be addressed proactively, both before and throughout the process, while considering the needs, perspectives and stakes of all involved. This requires a flexible approach to understanding diverse challenges, such as aligning expectations, clarifying roles, and adapting processes. Where possible, allowing some flexibility in timelines and budgets can help ensure meaningful participation, respond to emerging insights, and support community engagement.

To achieve this, it is essential to:

- **Define co-creation clearly**

At the start of the project, clarify what co-creation means to ensure everyone is on the same page and to avoid misunderstandings later. Differentiate between co-creation for, with, and by community members, and offer structured guidance, templates, and tools to maintain alignment and consistency throughout the process.

- **Clarify roles and decision-making processes**

Clarify and define roles and decision-making processes from the start. Recognize that not everyone may be familiar with designer-led approaches, and democratic decision-making may be new to some. Acknowledge that decision-making can be messy and complex. To ensure equity, actively communicate and clarify working dynamics for all participants, making sure everyone, especially community members, understands their role and the decision-making process at every stage.

- **Appoint dedicated co-creation facilitators who function as bridges between stakeholders**

Select facilitators with expertise in community engagement or provide targeted training for designers and tech developers on co-creating with marginalized communities. Facilitators should actively bridge cultural, linguistic, and geographical gaps or empower others to do so, ensuring all voices are heard, valued, and meaningfully included throughout the process.

- **Flexible timelines and inclusive budgets**

Provide as much flexibility as possible in project timelines to align with the natural rhythms and availability of the community, allowing for meaningful and sustained participation and opportunity to accommodate unforeseen needs that may arise within the process. Similarly, ensure that budgets are sufficient to address the complexity and diversity of the challenges being tackled, prioritizing needs and feedback of community members.

- **Keep design challenges concrete and actionable**

Break down large-scale social issues into smaller, locally relevant and actionable challenges. Define these challenges clearly, focusing on achievable, concrete outcomes that maintain momentum and engagement while addressing the specific needs of the community.

2.4. Principle 4. Open up to context

Principle four states that successful co-creation requires flexibility to accommodate diverse realities, including variations in perspectives, expertise, community structures, and cultural contexts. This means

being able to adapt to different needs and circumstances while critically examining assumptions about community members and stakeholders. Assumptions may not always align with actual dynamics, making it essential to remain open to learning and adjusting the process accordingly.

To achieve this, it is essential to:

- **Empower communities to define their own design challenges**

Instead of imposing predefined problems, empower community members in identifying and formulating their own design challenges. Facilitate inclusive processes that ensure local voices play a central role in shaping the pilot's direction from the outset. In addition, communities should be empowered in the delivery phase to enable them to sustain projects after the end of the pilot phase.

- **Ensure challenges reflect true community needs**

Commit to ongoing learning and adaptation by regularly engaging with community members. Continuously assess and refine the design challenge to ensure they align with the evolving needs and priorities of the community. Work closely with local experts and organizations to ensure solutions that are being developed remain relevant and impactful. Validate assumptions early on and often.

- **Build lasting support networks**

Leverage existing community structures and local knowledge to establish long-lasting support systems. Collaborate with community leaders and local experts to strengthen connections, ensuring the project's impact extends beyond initial engagement and supports long-term community resilience. When working with community leaders and/or local experts, ensure they genuinely represent the diverse needs and perspectives of the wider community, recognizing that even within communities, individuals may have varying ideas, interests, and concerns.

2.5. Principle 5. Frame the bigger picture

Principle five emphasizes that co-creation should be guided by a clear vision that aligns with broader social, ethical, and cultural objectives. This involves situating the project within a larger context that goes beyond immediate goals and considers long-term impact and sustainability. It is essential to design pilots with an eye toward their lasting influence, ensuring that the outcomes continue to benefit community members even after the project's conclusion. Additionally, co-creation should be informed by an understanding of the historical context that influences current efforts, acknowledging that past

experiences, future expectations, and evolving societal challenges all play a role in shaping the pilot's direction.

To achieve this, it is essential to:

- **Focus on quality over quantity**

Fewer, well-executed pilots are more impactful than many superficial initiatives. Invest resources and attention in fostering deep, meaningful engagement with communities, ensuring that each pilot leads to significant impact and avoids the pitfall of overextending efforts.

- **Ensure long-term sustainability**

Develop pilots with a focus on long-term community benefits, including clear transition and handover plans that guarantee continuity. Strengthen local capacity to support ongoing implementation, empowering communities to maintain and build upon the pilot's outcomes after its completion.

- **Prioritize data ethics in community engagement**

Ensure that all data practices—especially those involving sensitive personal information—are transparent, secure, and ethical for the duration of the project and after it has finished. This includes clearly communicating how data is collected, used, stored, and protected, and embedding these practices within all stages of the co-creation process. Special attention should be given when working with marginalized groups to safeguard trust and uphold ethical standards.

- **Establish continuous reflection and learning cycles**

Integrate regular reflection and feedback loops throughout the project lifecycle. Reflect on past experiences to understand what worked and what didn't, while analyzing previous pilots to identify successful elements at the community level. Use these insights to inform new pilots, avoiding past mistakes, and improving current efforts. Establish ongoing feedback processes that allow for real-time adjustments, ensuring the project stays aligned with community needs and adapts to evolving circumstances. This continuous cycle of reflection ensures that decisions are informed by past learnings, shaping both current and future initiatives effectively.

Fig 1. Visual of the principles of ethical and inclusive engagement

3. Co-creation Reboot Cardset

Based on the final principles of ethical and inclusive engagement, we developed the *Co-creation Reboot Card Set*. This tool incorporates reflective questions into the co-creation process to help pilots adapt their processes to better address the needs of the community. Reflexive practices in design are recognized for fostering critical awareness and deeper engagement with complex social issues. Reflection enables practitioners to challenge assumptions, embrace diverse perspectives, and iteratively refine their work.

In developing the card set, we aimed to creatively visualize the principles, rather than presenting them as a simple list of requirements. The card set organizes findings around five key principles of ethical and inclusive engagement. Each principle is accompanied by reflective questions to help stakeholders assess whether they are upholding ethical and inclusive standards throughout the co-creation process.

Additionally, the card set includes five wildcards that encourage users to think beyond the specific themes and explore broader aspects of their co-creation approach. By integrating these questions, pilot teams can engage in a continuous, iterative, and reflective process at every stage (see image 1 and 2). The card set's goal is to support pilot teams to identify blind spots, realign practices, and ensure that their approach remains responsive to the evolving needs of the communities they work with. The card set was distributed during the mid-term review meeting of the third pilot round and shared with participating and replicator city pilots. User feedback is being collected to inform and finalize the second iteration of the cards. The second iteration of the cards will be presented at the final event in Porto.

Fig 2 and 3. Examples of the Co-creation Reboot Cardset

5. Conclusion

In this deliverable, we have outlined the final principles of ethical and inclusive engagement, developed through research of the CommuniCity project pilots. These principles provide guidelines for stakeholders looking to adapt solutions to the unique needs of local communities, particularly marginalized groups. By focusing on inclusivity, strengthening connections, coordinating with empathy, remaining open to context, and framing the bigger picture, future co-creation initiatives in smart city contexts can ensure more equitable and sustainable outcomes. By embracing these principles, stakeholders can foster meaningful, lasting change that benefits communities far beyond the project's conclusion. We concluded this deliverable by describing the Co-Creation Reboot Card Set, which is designed to integrate reflexivity into the piloting process.

5. Reference

Costanza-Chock, Sasha. Design justice: Community-led practices to build the worlds we need. The MIT Press, 2020.

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